

Brussels skyscrapers: problems of identity. destroying in the name of protection

Introduction

In order to reach a better understanding of current policies as regards high-rise buildings, we need to be fully aware of the historical context in which these buildings emerged. Brussels is more than a thousand years old. The medieval urban fabric expanded continuously over nearly eight centuries. Though it underwent a few small-scale alterations with the erection of some neoclassical ensembles, it was not affected by large-scale urban mutations until the nineteenth century. Wide boulevards à la Haussmann were laid out in order to clean up specific neighbourhoods and make Brussels into a credible metropolis. This work (1867-1871) required covering the Senne all along its South-to-North run through the Pentagon¹, and pulling down several colourful working-class neighbourhoods.

At a later stage, as railway traffic kept increasing, there arose the idea of linking the South Station with the North Station (until then railway termini), with intermediate stations in the town centre. To carry out this junction, a broad swathe was cut through built-up areas in the centre (1901-1952). This once again meant razing entire neighbourhoods (1500 buildings were torn down, 12830 residents evicted). Apart from some general technical concerns, there was no overall master plan for rebuilding: the scars are still visible today: some plots remain unoccupied and those parts that have been rebuilt lack unity.

The tower to which we shall devote our attention below, the Lotto Tower, was built along the South-North junction in 1963 by the architect R. Goffaux, on the site where the d'Ursel mansion had once stood.

'50s and '60s: Megalomania

A series of major public works are again carried out in Brussels in the fifties and sixties. For the first time, skyscrapers rise against the Brussels skyline.

The delayed influence of CIAM, which had gathered in Brussels in 1930, is palpable in the language of urbanists, developers and policy-makers. It seems evident that, if it is to live up to its newly-acquired status of Capital of Europe, the city must be cleaned up, i.e. largely razed then rebuilt on rational principles. The belief in technological progress, the American myth and economic euphoria are to be at the root of oversized projects.

The authorities' chief goals are to maximize accessibility to cars, develop the tertiary sector and clear slums:

1. Genuine urban motorways, complete with tunnels and viaducts, provide access to the city centre. Work gets under way in the fifties, the prospect of the 1958 World Fair offering a temporary justification for the magnitude of the scheme. However, the construction works continue well beyond that date. Soon, residents begin protesting because of the damage done to their neighbourhoods and the resulting isolation from the rest of the city. Their grievances will go almost unheard. Parallel to road works, a great number of public car parks, covered or not, are built in the city centre. The urbanisation plan commissioned by the municipal authorities ('City of Brussels') in 1955 and executed by Tekhnè consultancy in 1962 conforms to the tendencies outlined above. The study's main concern was to improve traffic flow.

2. The tertiary sector is booming and the town centre soon abounds in office blocks. Several large-scale projects underpin this change.

- In 1937, the government decided to bring together into a modern and functional headquarters all the administrative services that were formerly accommodated in dilapidated buildings all over town. In 1955, it was decided that this giant headquarters for 20,000 civil servants was to be erected near the new Central Station, in a working-class neighbourhood already cruelly affected by the railway junction. Expropriations were carried out in a rush as early as 1956 because the authorities wanted most of the complex to be completed before the 1958 World Fair. The residents were offered scarcely any damages or social support. Due to technical problems, only the car park was completed in time, on sites cleared in a hurry. Not only was construction slowed down by financial troubles, but it also proved very difficult owing to the nature of the soil and to the heavy infrastructures required, so much so that it was to

continue until 1983. Ironically, the colossal Cité Administrative de l'Etat was never used to its full capacity. With the accomplishment of devolution in 1989, it was to be deprived of its main raison d'être, and is now gradually emptying.

- From 1962, the architects for the Structures planning office devised a master plan for redesigning the Quartier Nord (North District, 53 ha). This project, known as the Manhattan Plan, provided for some 80 office blocks (from 23 to 162 m tall) to be erected at the junction of several urban motorways. The Brussels World Trade Center, with its eight 102m towers, was to be the nerve centre of the neighbourhood. Between 10,000 and 11,000 residents had to go.² A promise had been made to build council houses to accommodate expropriated residents in the neighbourhood, but these were erected too late. The economic slump of the '70s put an end to this megalomaniac venture and only three WTC-towers were built. It was not until the '80s that new edifices started sprouting up again, along a prestigious axis entirely devoted to office blocks.

- From the 1950s the North-South junction undergoes rebuilding. The old neighbourhoods erected on a medieval street pattern were replaced by large monofunctional buildings occupying a full block, strewn along a wide boulevard that deepens the gap between uptown and downtown. These edifices, which are isolated, uncoordinated endeavours, make up a heterogeneous collection of architectural objects in various styles.

- From 1958, the European institutions expand rapidly in three nearby neighbourhoods East of the Pentagon. There too, nondescript mammoths (except, perhaps, for L. De Vestel's Berlaymont, on the site of a neoclassical convent) are erected, whose architecture is severely criticised and whose size also generates conspicuous discontinuities in the urban fabric.

3. Slum clearance, which had been a recurrent problem since industrialisation and the demographic thrust of the 19th century, was instituted by a 1953 law. The favoured solution was to replace the existing buildings with high-rise housing projects in conformity to the Athens Charter. Unfortunately, the numerous endeavours were too piecemeal, and forced upon the existing fabric in a brutal way³.

'70s and '80s: Reaction

Within the context of the May '68 commotion and the '70s oil crisis, the urbanistic options and realisations of the '50s and '60s are being questioned. Living in the city has become unbearable owing to never-ending construction works, traffic

congestion, the runaway expansion of office buildings. As a result, residents fled en masse to the suburbs⁴. The large-scale destruction of older neighbourhoods usually replaced with rather forbidding over-sized constructions is in part responsible for the city's loss of identity. The authorities' murky decision-making processes and their disregard for the residents would eventually spark off reactions from local residents' committees and pressure groups promoting a quality urban environment and heritage protection. The following are notable events:

- The early intervention (1967) of the non-profit organisation Quartier des Arts in order to defend and smarten up the high-standing uptown neighbourhoods.

- The famous 'battle of the Marolles' (1969), in which the vehement protests of the Comité des Marolles both stopped an extension of the Palace of Justice and obtained that this working-class neighbourhood be rehabilitated.

- The relentless activity of the Atelier de Recherche et d'Action Urbaine (Workshop for urban research and action) from 1968 onwards for more democratic decision-making in urbanistic matters, and for the defense of housing and industry against the spread of office space.

- The unifying action of Inter-Environnement Bruxelles (founded in 1971), which brings together more than 80 associations defending neighbourhoods and the environment.

Belgium's political institutions were modified in 1972. A new level of power was created, the 'Agglomération de Bruxelles', presiding over 19 municipalities. Until then, Brussels' affairs had been handled by the central government. Setting up an urban planning department within the Agglomération was a welcome development because the new administration was better prepared to pay attention to the inhabitants' demands. The Agglomération was deprived of its authority in 1987, but, in the wake of the federalisation process, Brussels' Capital Region was created in 1989 and was granted similar powers in urbanistic matters.

These political developments together with the tenacity of the residents' committees and other pressure groups were at the origin of improvements in:

- the decision-making process: a 1991 edict provides that requests for building permissions be made public and be subject to consultations;

- environmental protection: the Institut Bruxellois de Gestion de l'Environnement (Brussels Institute for Environment Management) is set up;

- heritage preservation: the Service des Monu-

ments et Sites (Department for Monuments and Sites) is set up, and a 1993 edict organizes preservation;

- the quality of public spaces, social aid, cultural development.

'90 and '00: Results

It is natural that many problems should remain, considering the inherent complexity of any large city's administration, especially in a country like Belgium with its many levels of power. However, the demands for a city that respects its inhabitants, its environment and its heritage have largely been taken into account by the City and the Capital Region since the '70s and more recently by the Federal State; witness the agreement for cooperation between the State and the Region for the year 2,000.

Attitudes have changed: decisions to pull down old buildings can no longer be taken lightly. Whereas in the Tekhnè plan of 1962 most of the Pentagon's buildings were regarded as 'unimprovable' or as slums, and therefore earmarked for demolition, in the 1979 zoning plan ('Plan de Secteur') most of the Pentagon has become worthy of preservation (in 'zones d'intérêt culturel, historique et esthétique'), and in the 1995 Regional Development Plan, the whole of the Pentagon is protected as a 'périmètre d'intérêt culturel, historique et esthétique'.

Heritage destruction has become taboo, and yet the municipal authorities support the demolition of Brussels' skyscrapers. This is a contradiction that is understandable in the light of the context outlined above. But it is also a contradiction that should be resolved. To that end, I shall now briefly introduce the towers located within the Pentagon and in neighbouring areas, and review the recent projects for them.

Most are found in the heart of the Pentagon, on its uptown borders, or in the North District.

- Lotto Tower, 1963, R. Goffaux and C. Heywang, 80 m Demolition and rebuilding project, H. Montois and Art & Build, 2000
- Stevens Tower, 1965-1966, A. Vanderauwera, 86 m
- Monnaie Tower, 1967-1971, J. Cuisinier, J. Gilson, A. & J. Polak, R. Schuiten, 63 m
- Philips Tower, 1967-1969, Structures, 63 m Demolition foreseen on expiration of 99-year lease (2066)
- South Tower, 1962-1967, R. Aerts & P. Ramon, Y. Blomme, J.F. Petit, A. Bressers, A. Van Acker, M. Lambrichs, A. Van Doosselaere, J. Hendrickx, 149 m Revamped facades with addition of geometric patterns
- Hilton Tower, 1967, H. Montois, 94 m
- Bastion Tower, 1967, R. Goffaux, 90 m Renovated

- Madou Tower, 1965, R. Goffaux, 112 m
- Astro Tower, 1976, A.J. De Doncker, 107 m
- P&V Tower, 1957 and 1965-1971, H. Van Kuyck Facades revamped in Art Nouveau style, Atelier d'Art Urbain, 2000
- Treasury Tower, 1968-1983, Groupe Alpha, M. Lambrichs, G. Ricquier, H. Van Kuyck, 141 m Projects for covering the outdoors service spine containing the elevators, originally meant to be marble-clad, with a vertical garden (H. Wieser, 1992, L. Schuiten, 1995)
- IBM Tower, 1978, Bresseleers, 80 m
- 'Rogier' International Centre (Martini Tower), 1958-1961, J. Cuisinier, 112 m, Demolition and rebuilding project, KohnPedersen-Fox
- Manhattan Center (Sheraton Tower), 1968-1973, Structures, 96 m
- World Trade Center, 1970-1974, Structures, 102 m
- Berlaymont, 1960-1970, L. De Vestel, A. & J. Polak, J. Gilson, 55 m Revamping project 1999-2000, P. Lallemand
- Charlemagne, 1967, J. Cuisinier

Facades refurbished in 1998 by Murphy & Jahn and Arias

Most of the towers were erected between the late fifties and early seventies. With the exception of the taller South Tower (149 m) and Treasury Tower (141 m), they are of moderate height, between 50 and 112 metres. Most are office towers, sometimes with shops on the ground floor (City's Administrative Centre, Rogier Centre, Madou Tower). The Lotto Tower (now empty), the Hilton and Sheraton are multi-use buildings incorporating hotels, offices and shops.⁵ They are scattered over town, except in the North District, where there is a concentration of towers.

From a technical point of view, most are curtain-wall structures, some of which only are genuine technical achievements (South Tower). >From an architectural point of view, functionalism is paramount. If some towers are exceedingly banal (Stevens Tower) or betray inadequate composition of the various volumes (City's Administrative Centre), some others achieve high-quality design and elegant proportions (Lotto Tower, Rogier Centre, P&V Building), or successful urban integration (Lotto Tower, Rogier Centre). However, some towers were erected regardless of their surroundings and caused discontinuities to emerge in the urban fabric (Treasury Tower, IBM Tower).

In the past few years, various projects to transform towers have seen the light of day. It is clear that functionalism is out of fashion, judging from the number of buildings due to be revamped in a postmodernist or high-tech style (South Tower, Berlaymont, Charlemagne, P&V Building, Cité Ad-

ministrative de l'Etat). One tower, AG's 'Blue Tower', was torn down in 1992 to make room for a cluster of buildings of traditional proportions inspired by historical classicism (Laeken Street). As to the Rogier Centre, it is to be demolished then built anew.

The City of Brussels has now defined a genuine urban policy: in its Municipal Development Plan (1999), high buildings have been found incompatible with urban morphology:

"Numerous office blocks are obsolete (1960s) (...). These are large monofunctional blocks whose aesthetics and setting do not fit well into a historic centre: towers, curtain walls, plots brought together... These create discontinuities in the urban fabric which are all the more undesirable because they are concentrated in one section of the Pentagon.

In the past few years, renovation has consisted either in rebuilding behind facades (Royale Belge, Josi, Le Continental), in restoring or updating buildings (SABENA, AG on the corner of Rue Royale and Rue du Gouvernement Provisoire), or in demolishing then rebuilding high-quality properties (AG's 'Blue Tower' on rue du Pont-Neuf). Though these three types of initiatives improve the image of the Centre, only the last one highlights and makes use of the quality of the building as a whole".⁶ (PCD, 1999, vol. 2a, p. 55).

The Philips Tower is to be razed on expiry of the lease in 2066. The PCD also mentions the possibility of rebuilding housing on the location of the Cité Administrative de l'Etat. The war against towers broke out in the wake of a renovation scheme for the Lotto Tower, the outcome of a contest in which close to 60 candidates had taken part. Three days before the winning projects were due to be displayed publicly, the Mayor declared that, from the Town Hall's balcony, the sight of this structure towering above the baroque houses on the Grand-Place was intolerable. As a result, investors were talked into lowering the tower by 30 metres. It then came out in the press that, far from being a mere whim of the Mayor's, a reduction of the tower was part and parcel of Brussels general urban policy.

Whereas high-rise structures were considered a panacea in the '50s and '60s, they have now fallen out of favour. It is as if they were responsible for all of Brussels' urban ills. Yet, they account for only a minor proportion of the town centre's office space. It is a bit facile to single out these landmarks in order to expose the inconsistencies of the cityscape. As often, architecture is burdened with the task of solving problems which in effect are essentially economic, political and social.

No doubt, against the background sketched above, the dislike for towers makes sense. From the outset, skyscrapers were associated with:

- heritage destruction;
- the megalomaniac joint projects of a few politicians and big developers;
- the dehumanisation of the city centre largely due to Brussels becoming a third-sector hub;
- a feeling of insecurity resulting from the building of large housing projects.

Besides, some specialists in urban and heritage matters have been at the forefront of the struggle against towers which, by their very presence, mar certain historic sites. Witness a 1982 paper⁷ in which eminent heritage experts paint a damning picture of towers, blaming them for the decrease in population in the town centre. After listing the various towers, the authors write:

"one wonders if there are any inhabitants left in this city. Where are they? Who are they? How do they live?"

The Lotto Tower is then singled out: "Not only did the building of this tower require the destruction of the mansion of the Dukes of Ursel, a precious historic edifice, but the tower enjoys the dubious privilege of being visible from the Grand-Place".

Questions

This condemnation of skyscrapers is endorsed by many within the intellectual élite who fought with determination for the rehabilitation of Brussels from the 1970s onwards. As a result of their action, these people enjoy a well-deserved recognition. But is it not a mistake to devote so much energy to the demolition of buildings which, after all, are part of today's heritage as well? Is there no way to preserve them while at the same time devising solutions to the problems of the city? Should one focus exclusively on those negative aspects of the general context at the expense of the manifest architectural qualities of some of the buildings?

It is easy to see that this hostility results from circumstances and not really from the buildings themselves. As I will tentatively try to show, Brussels' urban policy is aimed at the wrong targets.

The Lotto Tower is a case in point. Rather than rehashing the same old grievances against post-WWII buildings in general, it would make more sense to emphasise the Lotto Tower's numerous assets. Its volumes interplay subtly with the constraints of its immediate environment. Its quasi-triangular base covers the whole plot and adjusts to the straight lines or curvature of the streets around. The tower is thinner and also curved, but whereas the base is

curved outwards, the main facade of the tower is curved inwards. Thus, it harmonizes with the slope and with the streets facing it. In particular, Ravenstein Street, which makes a downwards bend as it widens towards the building whose hollow face seems to be made to contain space. Therefore, it causes no discontinuity with its surroundings. Moreover, its fairly modest proportions together with the lightness and transparency of its structure definitely keep it from becoming an overwhelming presence. The ground floor, with its large display windows, could accommodate shops and contribute to a busy street life. Unfortunately, continuity is broken by the adjacent building, whose structure is more heavy and closed-in, and is set back from the building line.

The municipal and regional authorities would like to attract a more affluent population to the centre. With a few minor changes, the tower, ideally located between the Grand-Place, the Central Station, the Fine Arts Centre, and Brussels' Royal Park, could provide quality housing with panoramic views. This could offset the much reviled impact of office blocks. The tower could also house a skydeck restaurant. However trivial the idea may seem, Brussels lacks panoramic viewpoints from which to admire the cityscape. A last point: the Lotto Tower is criticised for being visible from the Grand-Place and for standing on a site previously occupied by a wealthy mansion. Needless to say, the destruction of the tower will not bring back the mansion. Besides, I believe this scheme to be a symptom of the authorities' inability to take account fully of Brussels' inherent complexity, a hypocritical attempt to divert the public's attention from the real issues. The scheme testifies to Brussels' discomfort with modern architecture. Note that this is a city where the modern art wing of the Museum of Fine Arts (R. Bastin, 1973-84) was built underground for fear that it should clash with a neoclassical ensemble. This discomfort, however understandable, must be overcome. Otherwise, the risk is that few valuable testimonies of our period will be handed down to the future generations.

As a matter of fact, a change seems to be getting under way in some circles. Witness several punctual attempts to reclaim the city in its most unwelcoming quarters. For example, open-air parties and film projections were recently put on in the gardens of the Cité Administrative de l'Etat and along the North-South Junction viaduct. As part of the opening ceremonies for Brussels 2,000 (Cultural Capital of Europe), words were displayed at night on the facades of Brussels skyscrapers in huge letters made up of lit-up or occluded windows. Passersby were given a playful opportunity to rediscover these buildings. Some artists took pictures of the city from the

top of its towers, notably Marie-Françoise Plissart, who published a superb book of photographs in 1998. A 1999 exhibition set up by the Foundation for Architecture displayed impressive scale models and pictures of the capital's office blocks.

The pleasure of city life depends a great deal on how one looks at it, on the attitudes, positive or negative, one has towards it. It is paradoxical, and also deplorable, that urban heritage specialists should ignore an important period in the city's history. Such dispositions seem to nourish a policy aimed at reconstructing an ideal image of a historic centre untouched by modernity. Efforts to homogenize the cityscape appear to me to be misguided, all the more because they impair the ability to stand back and take in the full complexity and richness of the city.

As I am writing these lines, the request to demolish the Lotto Tower is being examined by the competent municipal services. It is likely to be granted approval soon, since it is in conformity with current urban policy and meets the Liberal Party Mayor's wishes.

NOTES

¹This term denotes the historic town centre as determined by the fourteenth-century ramparts, whose layout is reminiscent of this geometrical form.

²Figures vary wildly according to the sources: the City has 4,400 persons.

³Meiboom (1954-1964), Radis (1961), Potiers (1958-1965), Querelle (1971-1974), Brigittines (1964-1968), Minimes (1960-1964), Rempart des Moines (1961).

⁴Number of residents in the Pentagon in 1890: 159,000; 1996: 39,687.

⁵Housing projects in the Pentagon are usually smaller and rarely exceed fifteen storeys.

⁶This distinction made in the PCD could do with a clearer formulation.

⁷*Pierres et Rues* (1982: 94-100), which is the catalogue of an exhibition about urbanistic developments in Brussels over the past two centuries.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Archives d'Architecture Moderne (1982). *La reconstruction de Bruxelles*. Brussels: AAM.
- Aron J., Burniat P. et al. (1990). *Guide d'architecture moderne. Bruxelles et environs, 1890-1990*. Didier Hatier.
- Bekaert, G., Strauven F. (1970). *La construction en Belgique 1945-1970*. Brussels: CNC.
- Bekaert, G. (1996). *Architecture contemporaine en Belgique*. Brussels: Racine.
- Demey T. (1990-1992). *Bruxelles. Chronique d'une capitale en chantier*. Brussels: Paul Legrain, 2 vol.
- Lacour M. et al. (1987). *Morphologie urbaine à Bruxelles*. Brussels: CERA.
- La Fonderie & le Foyer Bruxellois (octobre 1997). *3000 Foyers Bruxellois, dossier n° 2 of Cahiers de la Fonderie*.
- Plissart M.F., Peeters, B. (1998). *Bruxelles, horizon vertical*. Brussels: Prisme Editions.

- Région de Bruxelles-Capitale (1997). *Ensembles architecturaux en région bruxelloise*. Brussels: Racine.
- Exhibition Catal. (1989). *50 ans Architecture Bruxelles*. Brussels: Marc Lacour.
- Exhibition Catal. (1982). *Pierres et rues. Bruxelles: croissance urbaine 1780-1980*. Brussels: F. Poot
- Exhibition Catal. (1999). *The Century of the Office. 1900-2000*. Brussels: Fondation pour l'Architecture.
- City of Brussels. *Plan Communal de Développement*. Preparatory document adopted by the Government on 04.02.1999. (The Municipal Development Plan is referred to as PCD in the text.)
- Articles by François Robert in Le Soir newspaper:
 - 07.10.1998: 'Pour dégager la vue du balcon de l'hôtel de ville, de Donnée veut étêter la tour de l'hôtel Westbury', p. 20.
 - 22.10.1998: 'De Donnée décapite la tour du Lotto. "Ce qui est petit est beau". Le nouveau credo urbanistique de la Ville vient de faire sa première victime', p. 21.
 - 16.03.1999: 'Première décapitation dans le Pentagone. La tour du Lotto rabotée de 12 étages'.
 - 09.04.1999: 'C'est dans le PCD... D'autres tours à raboter, dans le Pentagone?', p. 21.
 - 28.10.1999: 'Un milliard pour un nouvel hôtel, des bureaux et un "Health Center". Les Manhattan cow-boys de la place Rogier'.
 - 29.01.2000: 'Artesia apporte les sous, l'ARAU retire son recours au Conseil d'Etat. La tour Rogier reconstruite en 2001'.

KEYWORDS

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